

Compound of 1,4-dihydro-2,8-dimethylnaphthalene from the Ethyl Acetate Fraction Pangi Flesh (*Pangium Edule Reinw.*)

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Abstract

Pangi (*Pangium edule Reinw.*) is a native Indonesian plant that is often used by the community as food and traditional medicine. This research was conducted to isolate and identify the naphthalene compounds contained in the ethyl acetate fraction of Pangi fruit flesh (*Pangium edule Reinw.*). The isolation process was carried out using maceration and fractionation methods, for separation and purification of compounds using Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) and Gravity Column Chromatography methods and obtained isolate sub-fraction F_{3.1} with a sample weight of 7.3 mg. Identification of compounds using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance technique. Identification results of sub-fraction F_{3.1} isolate as a naphthalene derivative compound with the proposed name 1,4-dihydro-2,8-dimethylnaphthalene with the molecular formula (C₁₂H₁₄). **Keyword:** Isolation, Identification, *Pangium*, Naphthalene.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Pangi plant, known by the scientific name *Pangium edule Reinw.*, is a plant native to Indonesia [1]. The Pangi plant (*Pangium edule Reinw.*) belongs to the Flacourtiaceae family [2] and is one of the plants that produces fruit that can be consumed and has potential as medicine and spices [3]. Pangi plants are also used as snacks, seasonings, food preservatives, and antiseptics and medicines. Because of this, pangi plants are known as multipurpose plants [4,5].

Pangi plants, especially in North Sulawesi, are often used as food ingredients [6]. Pangi plants actually contain a lot of poison called hydrocyanic acid or HCN [6,7,8], besides containing HCN, it contains secondary metabolites such as saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and tannins [9].

Secondary metabolites are organic compounds with low molecular weight [10]. Secondary metabolites have a very important role as a support for a plant's survival in plant

adaptation to the environment [11].

Isolation and identification processes are needed to determine a class of secondary metabolite compounds [12,13]. Isolation includes extraction and chromatography techniques [14], while identification includes the process of analyzing the structure of an organic compound using the Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (RMI ¹H) and Carbon Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (RMI ¹³C) spectroscopy methods [15].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The tools used in this study were: 200 mL and 100 mL Beaker, 100 mL Measuring Cup, Funnel, Buchner Funnel, Stir Bar, Spatula, Measuring Pipette, Capillary Pipe, Rotary Evaporator Set, Gravity Column Chromatography Tool Set. Identification of compounds using the Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (RMI ¹H) and Carbon Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (RMI ¹³C) spectroscopy tools.

The materials used in the study as

samples were pangi fruit flesh (*Pangium edule* Reinw, 70% ethanol, technical methanol, ethyl acetate, n-hexane, aluminum silica gel TLC thin layer chromatography plate G 60 F₂₅₄ (E. merck 10554), H₂SO₄ solution 10% in ethanol, silica gel G 60 F₂₅₄ (E. merck 10554), deuterated chloroform and other materials such as Whatman 42 filter paper, aluminum foil and label paper.

Preparation, Extraction and Fractionation

Stages

The flesh of the Pangi fruit (*Pangium Edule* Reinw.) was peeled and separated from the seeds and 670.41 g was obtained and mashed using a blender. The sample was then dissolved in 70% ethanol solvent, left for 24 hours at room temperature to obtain filtrate and residue. The residue obtained was collected and macerated again using ethanol with the same procedure. In this stage maceration is carried out in different glass containers up to 1-3 cm above the sample, until the color of the filtrate becomes clear. Maceration was carried out for 6 x 24 hours. The next stage, the filtrate obtained was then evaporated using a rotary evaporator to obtain a thick ethanol extract.

The 20 g condensed ethanol extract was weighed, added with 20 g silica gel and crushed to obtain a mixed powder of extract and silica gel. The obtained powder was eluted successively with n-hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol using a Buchner funnel and vacuum. N-hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol filtrates were obtained, each filtrate was evaporated to become extracts, so that n-hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol extracts were obtained.

Compound Separation and Purification

The ethyl acetate extract was thin layer chromatographed with several volume ratios of solvents. Ethyl acetate : n-Hexane (1:9, 2:8, 3:7). The TLC results were sprayed with 10% H₂SO₄ as a stain remover in a fume cupboard and then

heated using a hot plate until stains appeared. The solvent ratio that produces a good separation pattern in TLC will be used as an eluent in gravity column chromatography. After getting the eluent then column chromatography.

In the process of separation gravitational column chromatography uses two phases, namely silica gel as the stationary phase and eluent with a solvent ratio that produces the best separation as the mobile phase. The results obtained from gravity column chromatography (Eluat) were accommodated in vials and then analyzed using TLC. Each eluate that has the same R_f is combined (fraction), then evaporated and then weighed.

The fractions obtained are then subjected to TLC to see the pattern of separation, and if there are still some visible spots in the tested fraction, column chromatography must be carried out. This step is continued until a relatively pure compound is obtained, if there is only one spot on the TLC plate, then the fraction can be said to be relatively pure which is called an isolate, then the isolate is evaporated and then weighed.

Determination of Isolate Structure

The isolates obtained were then identified using a Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectrometer (RMI ¹H) to determine the number of protons present in the compound and a Carbon Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectrometer (RMI ¹³C) which will provide information on the state of carbon atoms in an organic molecule.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sample Preparation, Extraction and Fractionation

Pangi (*Pangium Edule* Reinw.) flesh as much as 670.41 g was macerated using 70% ethanol for 6 x 24 hours and produced 2.4 liters of filtrate. The filtrate was then evaporated

using a rotary evaporator and a viscous ethanol extract of pangi (*Pangium Edule* Reinw.) fruit flesh of 29 g was obtained.

The 20 g condensed ethanol extract was weighed, added with 20 g silica gel and crushed to obtain a mixed powder of extract and silica gel. The obtained powder was eluted successively with n-hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol using a Buchner funnel and vacuum. 465 mL of n-hexane filtrate, 380 mL of ethyl acetate and 310 mL of methanol were obtained. The filtrate was evaporated and weighed to obtain 6.22 g of n-hexane, 0.41 g of ethyl acetate and 9.24 g of methanol.

Compound Separation and Purification

The first stage was storing the ethanol extract of Pangi fruit flesh, the ethyl acetate fraction, which had been weighed as much as 0.41 grams in the refrigerator. The second step is to find a suitable eluent ratio for gravity column chromatography, namely by conducting a TLC analysis. The ethyl acetate fraction was taken sufficiently and then analyzed by TLC using ethyl acetate : n-hexane in various ratios (1:9, 2:8, 3:7).

The results of the TLC analysis of the ethyl acetate fraction showed that the chromatogram pada with the eluent ratio of ethyl acetate : n-hexane (3:7) gave more stain/spot patterns compared to the other comparisons, indicated by the presence of 8 spots, so that the separation and purification of the ethyl acetate fraction for gravity column chromatography used the eluent ratio. Then the preparation of the apparatus for column chromatography was carried out, starting with immersing 27 g of silica gel (24 hours), then taking 0.41 g of the ethyl acetate fraction dissolved with approximately 1 mL of eluent added with a little silica gel, and separating it by chromatography the column used a solvent ratio of ethyl acetate: n-hexane = 3:7 (200 mL), the results of the column were accommodated

in 1 mL vials each, the eluate obtained was 120 vials.

Based on TLC, column chromatography eluate which has the same R_f was combined, evaporated and then weighed and 5 fractions were obtained. The 0.019 gram F₃ fraction was selected and then re-analyzed by column rechromatography using ethyl acetate: n-hexane (1:9) with silica gel as the stationary phase. The results of column rechromatography were collected in 1 mL vials each, 100 vials of eluate were obtained. Based on TLC, eluate with the same R_f value was combined, evaporated and then weighed and 1 sub-fraction was obtained. Each sub-fraction was then tested for purity using TLC, the TLC results for F_{3.1} showed that F_{3.1} (Isolate F_{3.1}) contained 1 stain, so that it could be stated that the compound resulted from isolate F_{3.1} was relatively pure.

Determination of Isolate Structure

A total of 7.3 mg of fraction 3.1 was selected and its structure was determined using Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (RMI ¹H) and Carbon Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (RMI ¹³C). F_{3.1} isolates were analyzed using Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (RMI ¹H) by dissolving the isolate in Chloroform-D (CDCl₃) at a frequency of 500 MHz.

The aromatic proton signal appears at a shift of δ 7.10; 7.52; ppm (d;d : 8.5; 8.5 Hz), signal at shift δH 1.66; 2.03 ppm indicates a methyl group, the proton signal on the double bond appears at a shift of δ H 5.77 ppm, and a cyclohexene proton signal appears at a shift of δ H 4.92 ; 4.90 ppm (d;d : 9.5;9.5 Hz).

Signal carbon chemical shift (δC) 30; 37 ppm indicates a CH₂ group identical, signal on chemical shift (δC) 22.7; 29.8 ppm indicates the presence of a CH₃ group identical, chemical shift signal (δC) 114; 119; 124 ppm identified the CH group identical, and

chemical shift signal (δC) 139.4; 124; 139; ppm identifies identical C groups.

Table 1. Proton and Carbon Chemical Shifts from the RMI 1H and RMI ^{13}C spectra

Position H and C	F3.1 Faction	
	δC	δH (ppm), mult, $J=$ Hz)
1	30	4.90, d;d, 9.5
2	139.4	-
3	114	5.77, s
4	37	4.92, d;d, 9.5
5	119	7.10, d, 8.5
6	119	7.52, d, 8.5
7	124	7.10, d, 8.5
8	139	-
9	139	-
10	124	-
11	29.8	2.03, p
12	22.7	1.66, p

Based on the description of the interpretation of the data, the RMI 1H and RMI ^{13}C spectra show that there are different

signals indicating the presence of naphthalene compounds.

Figure 1. Proposed Isolate Structure F_{3.1}(1,4-dihydro-2,8-dimethylnaphthalene).

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of isolation and identification of secondary metabolites from the ethyl acetate fraction of pangi fruit flesh, Isolate F₃ indicates a naphthalene derivative compound with the molecular formula (C₁₂H₁₄) and the proposed name: 1,4-dihydro-2,8-dimethylnaphthalene.

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